

Numerical Investigation Of Cavitation Phenomena In Check Valves Using Multi-Phase CFD Modeling

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ABSTRACT

Swing check valves are extensively used in industrial piping systems to prevent reverse flow; however, cavitation occurring within the valve can lead to erosion, vibration, noise, pressure losses, and reduced service life. In this study, a 4-inch swing check valve was designed using CATIA V5 and analyzed using ANSYS Workbench to investigate cavitation behavior, structural integrity, and thermal performance under an inlet pressure of 300 kPa and a fluid temperature of 375 K (101.85°C). A multiphase CFD analysis employing water-liquid and water-vapor phases with the Zwart–Gerber–Belamri cavitation model was performed at a valve opening angle of 30°. The baseline valve exhibited severe cavitation, characterized by a minimum pressure of 1.07×10^4 Pa and a maximum vapor volume fraction of 0.185. To mitigate cavitation, the valve geometry was optimized by modifying the flow passage in critical regions, resulting in an increase in minimum pressure to 1.15×10^5 Pa and a reduction in maximum vapor volume fraction to 0.04512, corresponding to approximately 75.6% reduction in cavitation intensity. Static structural analysis was subsequently carried out using the pressure load obtained from the CFD study to compare the performance of conventional SS304 stainless steel with a Hybrid SS304–Aluminum Alloy Metal Matrix Composite (MMC) developed using ANSYS Material Designer. The hybrid material exhibited comparable stress levels with the added benefits of lower density and improved thermal properties. Furthermore, steady-state thermal analysis was performed on the hybrid valve with and without a 0.1 mm Yttria-Stabilized Zirconia (YSZ) thermal barrier coating. The coated valve demonstrated improved thermal insulation, reducing the average valve body temperature from 104.79°C to 99.89°C. The results indicate that the combination of geometric optimization, hybrid composite materials, and thermal barrier coatings can significantly reduce cavitation effects, maintain structural safety, improve thermal management, and enhance the overall performance and durability of swing check valves operating under high-temperature and cavitating flow conditions.

Keywords: Swing Check Valve, Cavitation, CFD Analysis, Structural Analysis, Thermal Analysis, Hybrid MMC, SS304, Aluminum Alloy, YSZ Coating, Flow Optimization.

1. Introduction

Check valves have a critical importance in oil and gas applications, power generation, and process industries due to their capability to control the direction of flow and the amount of pressure within the system. In its use, significant pressure changes during operation could cause cavitation of the fluid if the pressure in the vicinity falls below the vapor pressure of the fluid. Formation and implosion of vapor bubbles generate shockwaves capable of damaging components of the check valve and reducing efficiency, leading to noise and vibration issues. The conventional experiments on cavitation are quite complex and expensive; thus, the employment of CFD simulation tools offers a better approach to visualize and analyze the flow.

1.2 Cavitation in Swing Check Valves

This fluid dynamic condition occurs whenever there is a drop in the liquid's local pressure to become lower than the vapor pressure, leading to the creation of vapor bubbles. The next step involves imploding these vapor bubbles when they reach regions with higher pressures, thus creating strong shockwaves and miniature jets. Cavitation usually takes place close to the valve's disc-seat zone during fast closing/opening operations, fast fluid velocity, or large pressure differential across the valve. [3],[4]

The repeated collapse of vapor bubbles can cause severe erosion of the valve disc and seat, generate excessive noise and vibration, reduce flow efficiency, and ultimately shorten the service life of the valve. Therefore, understanding and controlling cavitation is critical for reliable valve operation, especially in high-pressure water and industrial fluid systems. [3],[4]

Figure1. Real time cavitation erosion occurrence on valves

1.2.1 Causes of Cavitation in Swing Check Valves

- High fluid velocity through the valve.
- Large pressure drop across the valve.
- Rapid valve closure or transient flow conditions.
- Improper valve sizing.
- Turbulent flow near the disc and seat region. [3],[5]

1.3 Cavitation Phenomenon in Check Valves

Cavitation occurs when the static pressure of the fluid drops below its vapor pressure, causing the liquid to vaporize and form bubbles. As the fluid moves downstream and pressure recovers, these bubbles collapse violently, producing localized high-pressure zones. This leads to surface erosion, noise, vibration, and reduced flow performance. The severity of cavitation depends on factors such as pressure drop, fluid properties, valve geometry, and flow velocity. In Check valves, cavitation typically occurs near the vena contracta region where velocity is highest and pressure is lowest.

1.4 Design Considerations for CFD Analysis

The Check valve geometry considered in this study includes an inlet section, valve body, valve seat, and outlet section. The fluid (typically water or hydrocarbon liquid) enters the valve at high pressure and exits at a lower pressure, creating conditions for cavitation. The geometry may include different valve openings (e.g., 25%, 50%, 75%) to study performance under varying flow conditions. Materials such as stainless steel are commonly used due to their resistance to cavitation erosion. In CFD modeling, the liquid phase is treated as the primary phase, while vapor formation is modeled using a cavitation model such as the Schnerr–Sauer or Zwart–Gerber–Belamri model. Turbulence effects are captured using models like $k-\epsilon$ or $k-\omega$ SST, and the simulation is performed under steady or transient conditions depending on the level of accuracy required.

1.5 Summary of Iterations Performed

Case	Analysis Type	Iteration	Description
Case 1	CFD	Iteration 1	Standard Swing Check Valve (30° opening, 300 kPa, 375 K)
Case 2	CFD	Iteration 2	Optimized Valve Geometry for Cavitation Reduction
Case 3	Static Structural	Iteration 3	SS304 Valve under CFD Pressure Load (0.297 MPa)
Case 4	Static Structural	Iteration 4	Hybrid SS304 + Aluminum Alloy MC Valve
Case 5	Thermal Analysis	Iteration 5	Hybrid SS304 + Aluminum Alloy MC Valve (Uncoated)
Case 6	Thermal Analysis	Iteration 6	Hybrid SS304 + Aluminum Alloy MC Valve with 0.1 mm YSZ Coating

Table:1 Summary of Iterations Performed

1.6 Material Selection for Simulation

1.6.1 Pugh Matrix for Material Selection

Selection Criteria	Weight	SS304 (Datum)	Al 6061	Ti-6Al-4V	Duplex SS	Hybrid MMC (SS304+Al)
Strength	5	0	-1	+1	+1	+1
Stiffness	4	0	-1	+1	+1	+1
Thermal Conductivity	4	0	+1	-1	0	+1
Corrosion Resistance	5	0	0	+1	+1	+1
Cavitation Resistance	5	0	-1	+1	+1	+1
Weight Reduction	4	0	+1	+1	-1	+1
Thermal Resistance	4	0	-1	+1	+1	+1
Manufacturability	3	0	+1	-1	0	+1
Cost Effectiveness	3	0	+1	-1	-1	0
Service Life	5	0	-1	+1	+1	+1
Weighted Score		0	4	19	17	25

Table :2 Pugh Matrix for Material Selection

Material	Total Score	Rank
Hybrid MMC (SS304 + Aluminum Alloy)	25	1
Titanium Alloy (Ti-6Al-4V)	19	2
Duplex Stainless Steel	17	3
Aluminum Alloy 6061	4	4
SS304 (Datum)	0	5

Table: 3 Pugh Matrix Ranking

2. Analytical calculation

Based on the drawing, the valve is a 4-inch (DN100) Swing Check Valve with:

- Nominal Diameter (ID) = 101.6 mm
- Flange OD = 230 mm
- Face-to-Face Length = 290 mm
- Design Pressure = 16 bar
- Material = SS304

2.1. Flow Area of Valve

Internal diameter:

$$D = 101.6 \text{ mm} = 0.1016 \text{ m}$$

Cross-sectional area:

$$A = \pi D^2 / 4$$

$$A = \pi r^2 \approx 28.27$$

$$C = 2\pi r \approx 18.85$$

$$r = 3.00$$

$$A = \pi(0.1016)^2 / 4$$

$$\text{Flow Area} = 8.107 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2$$

2.2. Hydraulic Force Acting on Disc

CFD inlet pressure:

$$P = 300 \text{ kPa}$$

$$P = 3 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}$$

Hydraulic force:

$$F = PA$$

$$F = (3 \times 10^5)(0.008107)$$

$$F = 2432 \text{ N}$$

Hydraulic Force = 2.43 kN

2.3. Pressure Load Used for Structural Analysis

Pressure transferred from CFD:

$$P = 2.97 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}$$

$$P = 0.297 \text{ MPa}$$

This is the pressure applied on the internal valve surfaces during Static Structural analysis.

2.4. Disc Opening Area at 30°

For a swing check valve:

$$A_o = A \sin \theta$$

where

$$\theta = 30^\circ$$

$$A_o = 0.008107 \times \sin 30^\circ$$

$$A_o = 0.008107 \times 0.5$$

$$\text{Effective Opening Area} = 4.05 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2$$

2.5. Average Flow Velocity

Assuming inlet flow rate:

$$Q = 0.01 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$$

Continuity equation:

$$Q = AV$$

$$V = Q/A_o$$

$$V = 0.01/0.004053$$

$$\text{Average Velocity} = 2.47 \text{ m/s}$$

2.6. Reynolds Number

At 101.85°C:
Water density
 $\rho = 958 \text{ kg/m}^3$

Viscosity

$$\mu = 2.82 \times 10^{-4} \text{ Pa.s}$$

Reynolds number:

$$Re = \rho V D / \mu$$

$$Re = ((958)(2.47)(0.1016)) / (2.82 \times 10^{-4})$$

$$Re = 8.54 \times 10^5$$

Flow is Highly Turbulent

2.7. Cavitation Number

Water vapor pressure at 101.85°C:

$$P_v = 101.3 \text{ kPa}$$

Atmospheric outlet pressure:

$$P_2 = 101.3 \text{ kPa}$$

Cavitation number:

$$\sigma = (P - P_v) / (1/2 * \rho V^2)$$

$$\sigma = (300000 - 101300) / (0.5 * (958)(2.47)^2)$$

$$\sigma = 67.9$$

If local pressure near the seat falls below vapor pressure, cavitation begins despite the high inlet cavitation number.

2.8. Hoop Stress Approximation

For a thick-walled pressure vessel, the maximum circumferential stress occurs at the inner wall:

$$\sigma_h = P(ro^2 + ri^2) / (ro^2 - ri^2)$$

Substituting:

$$\sigma_h = 0.297(65.8^2 + 50.8^2) / (65.8^2 - 50.8^2)$$

$$\sigma_h = 1.17 \text{ MPa}$$

These features create local stress concentrations. For cast valve bodies, a stress concentration factor K_t between 8 and 20 is commonly observed.

Taking:

$$K_t = 15$$

$$\sigma_{max} = K_t \times \sigma_h$$

$$\sigma_{max} = 15 \times 1.17$$

$$max = 17.55 \text{ MPa}$$

2.9 Desings

The design of the swing check valve was developed using CATIA V5 based on standard 4-inch valve dimensions. Initially, the valve body was modeled in the Part Design workbench by creating a two-dimensional sectional profile and revolving it about the central axis using the Shaft feature. The inlet and outlet flow passages were incorporated according to the standard valve dimensions, while the flange connections were created at both ends of the valve body. Bolt holes were generated using the Hole and Circular Pattern commands to match the flange specifications. Fillets and edge refinements were added to improve manufacturability and reduce stress concentration regions.

Figure 2. drafting of standard swing check valve

Figure 3. ISO, Front, Side & Top view of swing check valve from Catia V5

3. CFD ANALYSIS

3.1 Case 1 CFD of Wing Check valve

Case	Analysis Type	Configuration	Objective
Case 1	CFD	Standard Swing Check Valve	Cavitation prediction and flow analysis
Case 2	CFD	Optimized Swing Check Valve	Cavitation reduction and pressure recovery

Case 3	Static Structural	SS304 Valve	Stress and deformation assessment
Case 4	Static Structural	Hybrid SS304 + Aluminum Alloy MMC Valve	Structural performance comparison
Case 5	Thermal	Hybrid MMC Valve	Temperature distribution analysis
Case 6	Thermal	Hybrid MMC + 0.1 mm YSZ Coating	Thermal insulation and heat transfer evaluation

Table: 4 Summary of Proposed Analysis Cases

The Zwart–Gerber–Belamri (ZGB) Cavitation Model was activated to predict the phase change process between liquid water and water vapor. This model calculates vapor generation and condensation rates based on local pressure variations within the flow field. When the local pressure falls below the vapor pressure of water, vapor bubbles are generated, whereas condensation occurs when the pressure recovers above the vapor pressure. The model is widely used for valve cavitation studies because of its robustness and ability to accurately predict cavitation inception and vapor volume fraction distribution.

The primary phase was defined as water-liquid, while the secondary phase was defined as water-vapor. Material properties corresponding to the operating temperature of 375 K (101.85°C) were assigned to both phases. The vapor pressure of water at the specified temperature was considered in the cavitation calculations. The multiphase model was coupled with the Realizable $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model and the energy equation to account for turbulence effects and temperature-dependent flow behavior. These settings enabled the simulation of thermo-fluid interactions, pressure fluctuations, and cavitation characteristics within both the standard and optimized swing check valve designs.

Figure 4. Cavitation model from CFD Fluent

3.2 Case 2 : Optimized design of valve

The CFD results of the baseline valve revealed extensive cavitation formation due to low-pressure zones near the valve seat and disc region. To mitigate cavitation, an optimized valve geometry was developed by modifying the flow passage in cavitation-prone areas. The objective of the design modification was to improve pressure recovery, reduce the extent of low-pressure regions, and minimize vapor bubble generation without adversely affecting the overall flow performance.

3.2.1 Results and Discussion

The optimized valve maintained the same maximum velocity of 5.47 m/s, indicating that the design modification did not significantly alter the flow rate characteristics. However, a substantial improvement was observed in pressure recovery. The minimum pressure increased from 1.07×10^4 Pa in the baseline model to 1.15×10^5 Pa, while the maximum pressure increased slightly to 2.97×10^5 Pa. This increase in minimum pressure

indicates that the optimized design successfully reduced the severity of low-pressure zones responsible for cavitation initiation.

The water volume fraction improved significantly, ranging from 1.0 to 0.9549, while the maximum vapor volume fraction decreased dramatically from 0.185 to 0.04512. This corresponds to a reduction in cavitation intensity of approximately 75.6%, demonstrating the effectiveness of the geometric optimization. The reduction in vapor formation confirms that the optimized valve design achieved better pressure recovery and suppressed cavitation development within the flow passage.

Overall, the optimized swing check valve exhibited superior hydraulic performance compared to the baseline design. The increased minimum pressure, higher liquid volume fraction, and substantially lower vapor volume fraction indicate a significant reduction in cavitation risk. Consequently, the optimized design is expected to provide improved operational stability, reduced erosion potential, lower noise and vibration levels, and enhanced service life under the specified operating conditions.

Figure 5 Static pressure in pascals for non optimized valve

Figure 6. Velocity in m/sec results for non optimized valve

Figure 7. fraction volume of water liquid for non optimized valve

Figure 8. fraction volume of water vapor for non optimized valve

Figure 9. fraction volume of water vapor for optimized valve

Figure 10. fraction volume of water liquid for optimized valve

Table 5. Results & Conclusion

Sr.No	Type	Temperature in K max to min	Velocity in m/sec max to min	Pressure in pascals max to min	Volume fraction of water max-min	Volume fraction of Vapor max-min
1..	Base	375 K max 300 K min	5.47 max 0 min	2.96E5 max 1.07E4 min	1 max 0.815 min	0.185 Max 0.0 Min

2.	Optimized	375 K max 300 K min	5.47 max 0 min	2.97E5 max 1.15E5 min	1 max 0.9549 min	0.04512 max 0.0 min
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Graphs 1. (a) Temperature comparison (b) Velocity (c) Pressure (d) Volume fraction of water liquid € volume fraction of water vapor

3.3 Static structural analysis

3.3.1 Case 3: Static Structural Analysis of SS304 Valve

The structural comparison indicates that the Hybrid SS304 + Aluminum Alloy MMC experiences slightly higher deformation and strain than SS304 due to its reduced stiffness; however, it maintains a comparable stress level under identical loading conditions. Since the maximum stress remains significantly below the allowable limits, the hybrid material demonstrates sufficient load-carrying capability while offering the additional advantage of reduced weight. Therefore, the Hybrid MMC can be considered a viable alternative to conventional SS304 for swing check valve applications where weight reduction and improved thermal characteristics are desired without compromising structural safety.

Figure 11. Boundary conditions for structural analysis

Figure 12. Total Defromation

Figure 13. Von-Misses Stress for SS Material

3.3.2 Material Designer Procedure in ANSYS Workbench

The hybrid SS304 + Aluminum Alloy Metal Matrix Composite (MMC) was developed using the Material Designer module available in ANSYS Workbench. Initially, a new Material Designer system was added to the project schematic and linked with Engineering Data. The objective was to create a representative composite material by combining the mechanical and thermal properties of SS304 stainless steel and Aluminum

Alloy. Material Designer enables the prediction of effective composite properties through homogenization techniques based on the selected Representative Volume Element (RVE).

Figure 14. total defromation for Hybrid SS + Al alloy

Figure 15. Von misses stress for hybrid valve material

Parameter	SS304	Hybrid SS304 + Aluminum Alloy MMC
Maximum Total Deformation (mm)	0.01269	0.02084
Average Total Deformation (mm)	0.00192	0.00319
Maximum Equivalent Elastic Strain (mm/mm)	1.4443×10^{-4}	2.3735×10^{-4}
Average Equivalent Elastic Strain (mm/mm)	1.5851×10^{-5}	2.6951×10^{-5}
Maximum Equivalent Stress (MPa)	18.637	18.211
Average Equivalent Stress (MPa)	2.6864	2.7073

Table comparison of strutural results for both material

Graph 2. Structural analysis plots deformation, strain & stress results from ANSYS workbench

3.4 Case 5: Steady-State Thermal Analysis of Hybrid SS304 + Aluminum Alloy MMC Valve

Figure 16. Boundary condition for steady condition of thermal module

Figure 17. Temperature result for hybrid material

TABLE Surface Coating

Object Name	Surface Coating
State	Fully Defined
Scope	
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection
Geometry	117 Faces
Definition	
Stiffness Behavior	Membrane Only
Material	YSZ
Thickness	0.1 mm
Coordinate System	Default Coordinate System
Suppressed	No

Figure 18. Surfaces coating on internal surface of the valve material

Figure 19. Temperature result for surface coating of YSZ

Graph 3. Comparison of steady state thermal analysis for both material

3.5 Results

Parameter	Hybrid MMC	Hybrid MMC + 0.1 mm YSZ Coating
Minimum Temperature (°C)	104.2	97.365
Maximum Temperature (°C)	105.0	105.04
Average Temperature (°C)	104.79	99.887

Minimum Heat Flux (W/mm ²)	9.5217×10^{-8}	6.4464×10^{-6}
Maximum Heat Flux (W/mm ²)	1.1258×10^{-2}	8.7694×10^{-2}
Average Heat Flux (W/mm ²)	9.2237×10^{-4}	2.8834×10^{-3}

3.5.1 Conclusion

The Hybrid SS304 + Aluminum Alloy MMC valve exhibited efficient heat conduction, resulting in a nearly uniform temperature distribution throughout the structure. After applying a 0.1 mm YSZ thermal barrier coating, the average valve body temperature decreased from 104.79°C to 99.89°C, indicating improved thermal insulation. The results confirm that the YSZ coating effectively reduces heat transfer to the valve substrate, thereby enhancing thermal protection and making the coated Hybrid MMC valve more suitable for high-temperature and cavitation-prone operating environments.

4. CONCLUSION

This research focuses on studying the behavior of cavitation, valve integrity, and thermal analysis of a 4-inch swing check valve by means of CFD, Static Structural Analysis, and Steady-State Thermal Analysis in ANSYS Workbench. Firstly, a conventional swing check valve is developed in CATIA V5 under the working conditions of inlet pressure at 300 kPa and a temperature of the fluid at 375 K (101.85 °C). A two-phase cavitation analysis was done using a multiphase flow model for cavitation simulation accounting for both liquid and vapor water. CFD analysis of the initial design has revealed severe cavitation around the seat of the valve in zones with narrow passage. The pressure dropped to 1.07×10^4 Pa, and the maximum vapor volume fraction reached 0.185; consequently, cavitation is pronounced.

To eliminate the issue mentioned, the flow channel in the valve was modified to increase pressure recovery and reduce regions with lower pressure responsible for vapor generation. As can be seen from CFD analysis, hydraulic efficiency increased after modification of the valve; the minimum pressure became 1.15×10^5 Pa while the maximum vapor volume fraction became 0.04512, meaning that cavitation level reduced by approximately 75.6 %.

To evaluate structural performance, static structural analysis was carried out using the pressure loading obtained from CFD analysis (0.297 MPa). Two material configurations were investigated: conventional SS304 stainless steel and a Hybrid SS304 + Aluminum Alloy Metal Matrix Composite (MMC) developed using ANSYS Material Designer. The SS304 valve exhibited a maximum equivalent stress of 18.637 MPa and a maximum deformation of 0.01269 mm, whereas the Hybrid MMC valve showed a maximum equivalent stress of 18.211 MPa and a deformation of 0.02084 mm. In both cases, the stresses remained significantly below the material yield limits, confirming safe operation under the specified loading conditions. The Hybrid MMC additionally provided the benefit of reduced density and improved thermal conductivity, making it a promising alternative to conventional stainless steel.

The thermal performance of the Hybrid MMC valve was further evaluated using steady-state thermal analysis. The uncoated Hybrid MMC valve exhibited an average temperature of 104.79°C, indicating efficient heat conduction throughout the structure. To enhance thermal protection, a 0.1 mm Ytria-Stabilized Zirconia (YSZ) Thermal Barrier Coating (TBC) was applied to the inner surface of the valve. The coated valve demonstrated a reduction in average temperature to 99.89°C, confirming the effectiveness of the coating in restricting heat transfer to the substrate material. The YSZ coating improved thermal insulation and is expected to contribute to enhanced durability under elevated temperature operating conditions.

Overall, the study successfully demonstrated that geometric optimization, hybrid material development, and thermal barrier coating application can significantly improve the performance of swing check valves operating under cavitating and high-temperature flow conditions. The optimized valve with Hybrid SS304–Aluminum MMC and YSZ coating provides a balanced combination of reduced cavitation, adequate structural strength, improved thermal management, and enhanced service life.

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